

Additional file 7: Principal component analyses (PCA) for *Pinus pinaster* (above) and *Fusarium circinatum* (below) rlog data of the differential expression gene analysis (DESeq2). In red: mock-inoculated samples; in blue: inoculated samples at 3 dpi; in green: inoculated samples at 5 dpi; in yellow: inoculated samples at 10 dpi.

